

Mobile Based Appointment System for the Lecturers and Students for University of Technology and Applied Sciences – Shinas: A Study on Alternative Communication Tool

¹ Jumana Ibrahim Al Balushi, ² Jawaher Matar Al Washah, ³ Aaisha Ali Al Kaabi, ⁴ Anthony Mendoza
Madlambayan

^{1, 2, 3, 4} University of Technology & Applied Sciences - Shinas

¹66J1867@shct.edu.om, ²66S1812@shct.edu.om, ³66J1918796@shct.edu.om, ⁴anthony.madlambayan@shct.edu.om

Abstract:

In any university setting, communication plays an important role between lecturers and students because it serves as a link to inform each other about important issues that needs to be addressed. The researchers would like to proposed a mobile-based appointment system for students and lecturers of University of Technology and Applied Sciences - Shinas as an additional and alternative platform for setting appointments and as a safe and recognized communication tool. The researchers would like also to make a study about alternative means of communication aside from the existing Student Advising System (SAS) and Outlook application as the communication tools between lecturers and students. To give the researchers the needed data to design the propose system, the researchers will conduct a survey to determine the problems on the existing communication tools and to determine some features that can be added to the propose system that may not be in the existing communication tools. The researchers believed that the propose system can be used as an additional and alternative communication platform that can be used by the lecturers and students of UTAS –Shinas.